

Corti

Title: Deep learning decision support in critical medical conversations

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INTRODUCTION:

Emergency service agents are single-handedly responsible for decisions that may result in fatal outcomes. The conversations are highly stressful and unstructured, which increase the probability for faulty conclusions. In this study we present Corti's machine learning models that passively listen in on emergency calls and propose possible diagnostics to the agent.

AIM:

To save lives by decreasing the rate of faulty diagnostics made by emergency service agents.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This technology extract features directly out of the audio signal represented by a caller and an agent. It correlates audio features, such as breathing patterns, together with the conversational context in order to conclude the final diagnostics. The technology is made from supervised, semi-supervised and unsupervised machine learning algorithms parameterized by convolutional and recurrent neural networks.

A study has been performed on more than 3 years of historical emergency phone calls (approximately 140,000 calls a year). Another study has been performed live within a period of 4 months. The applied methodology entails an evaluation of the false positives and false negatives and a comparison to the performance without the machine learning models. This concludes in a final estimation of the number of people saved by the technology.

RESULTS:

The results show close to 20% improvement in predictions with a false positive rate of only 2%. A paper is currently being published to the Lancet journal.

CONCLUSIONS:

In this study we have proven that we can utilize the power of deep learning to predict diagnostics from highly unstructured emergency service conversations.

KEYWORDS:

deep learning; machine learning; automatic speech recognition; audio classification; medical machine learning.

BIOGRAPHY:

Lars Maaløe has completed his PhD within machine learning from the Technical University of Denmark. He is the VP of Science at Corti, a company that augments medical conversations.